

Examining Mean World Syndrome Effect Cultivated in Youth by Exposure of Disaster of Apocalyptic Films

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Abstract

The research article examined the "Mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth of by exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films." The aim of the study is to find the relationship between frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films and the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth. The research paper adopted quantitative research method to analyze the mean world syndrome effect have been surveyed purposively. Questionnaire was prepared and administered face-to-face to three hundred respondents of three Universities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. Factor analysis was applied to analyze the data and to establish the relation between variables, the method of Pearson correlation was used. Findings revealed that relation between the exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films and mean world syndrome effect is significant at level .05 on light and heavy viewers that validated the hypothesis; H1 that, "the more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth."

Introduction

The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth. Mean world syndrome effect comprised of fearfulness and perception of world through media. According to cultivation theory, the frequent exposure to the disastrous content of media is evident that audience perceive the real world in distorted way. The more exposure to disastrous content of films, the more likely to view the world as dangerous place as well to live due to fearfulness. It shows influence of media content is more on heavy viewers as compared to light viewers of the similar demographics. 300 respondents have been surveyed randomly by Gerbner to introduce the theory and later collectively by Gerbner and Gross to find the effect of media violence among various type of viewership. The regular exposure to media results the change in attitudes and behaviors of viewers and they started believing that whatever is presented on media is a true picture of reality. Therefore, more exposure to violence, fear and disaster, more violent is the behavior of viewer and more it is perceived real (p. 172). According to Gerbner, heavy viewers are exposed to media content for more than four hours/day and less than two per day are light viewers (Griffin, 2012a, p.366). As Gerbner, surveyed undergraduates and found that there is statistically significant relationship between consuming media content and fearfulness of becoming the victim of a crime (Griffin, 2012b, p.377). Gerbner also examined that whoever consume more media, more change occurs in thoughts and perception that leads to "Mean World Syndrome" (Bryant & Mirion, 2004, p. 662). Hence, more exposure to media leads the viewers to judge the world more dangerous and disastrous than it in reality (Hughes & Michael, 1980, p. 287). Heavy viewers think that the world constructed by media is real (Gerbner, Gross, Morgan, Signorielli, & Jackson-Beeck, 1979, p. 177).

Rationale of the Study

According to the literature review, studies have been conducted on the effect of audience analysis related to disaster shown in apocalyptic films in developed countries but it is deeply needed in developing or underdeveloped countries, research needed to be conducted. This study has investigated the mean world syndrome effect of disaster of apocalyptic films on youth of Pakistan. Hence, in the media richness era where there is exposure to media is tri-fold due to Netflix and other such services that are providing accesses to films, drama and seasons of all genres, had drastically changed the perception of youth about the world around. Therefore, a revisit is necessary to record the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth by exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films in Pakistan in the recent era. Youth of Pakistan takes active part in every occupation here and as an active user of media, is affected by the film content regardless of socio-economic status or other demographics.

The Selection of Universities

Three universities have been selected; Bahria University Islamabad, Foundation University Rawalpindi and International Islamic University, Islamabad. The Undergraduate students of various department have been selected randomly.

Selection of Apocalyptic Films

The films contain excessive amount of disaster, fear and violence from two years i.e. 2016 and 2017, comprising of more than one-hour time. The type of disaster is natural, alien and biological warfare. The selected films were:

1. Geostorm – 2017(1hr 49mins) (Natural Disaster).
2. The 5th wave – 2016(1hr 52mins) (Alien Disaster).
3. Daylight's end- 2016(1hr 45mins) (Biological Warfare).
4. Here alone- 2016 (1hr 38mins) (Biological Warfare).

Research Questions

RQ1: To what extent, exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films cultivate mean world syndrome effect in youth.

RQ1a: To what extent, exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films cultivate fearfulness in youth.

RQ1b: To what extent, exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, cultivates real world perception in youth.

Hypotheses

Main Hypothesis

H1: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth.

H1a: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the fearfulness in youth.

H1b: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the real world perception in youth.

Objectives

The study has designed to fulfill the following objective;

To examine the relation between the mean world syndrome effects cultivated in youth of Rawalpindi and Islamabad due to exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films.

Statement of the Problem

Cultivation theory analyzes the effect of frequently exposed (violence and fearful) content related to disaster on the heavy and light viewers. The content of apocalyptic films amplifies the feelings of fearfulness and violence and change the perception of world around the viewer. Viewers think that content shown in apocalyptic films is real leading to mean world syndrome. To revisit the cultivation theory, this research needed to be done in Pakistan's context to find the relation between frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films and mean world syndrome effect in youth.

Apocalyptic films were produced using powerful computer effects to introduce viewers to the world of fiction that kept them away from real world, therefore this research examines to what extent the relation exists between the mean world syndrome effects cultivated in youth of Rawalpindi and Islamabad and exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films.

Literature Review

Lippmann explored that the media help in accepting the world around us and that it is impossible for a person to fully recognize the society due to incomplete view about the society. Therefore, according to Lippmann, to get the view of the world, the world must be reconnoitered, registered or imagined. One can create picture in the head and the world around us (1922, p. 18). Hence making logic of the composite nature of the environment and locate himself in it (p.11). Griffin exclaimed that more exposure to media in viewing TV expected to see the 'real world' through the lenses of TV (2012, p.370). The study, "Cultivation Effects of Television Broadcasting and Online Media", investigated that in the period of social media, Online Media is so common that the whole world can use their electronic devices to access in anytime and anywhere. At the same time, TV is termed as traditional media, but its importance and power cannot be denied (Lee, Chul-joo&Niederdeppe, Jeff, 2011, p.731).

The study aimed to survey 258 undergraduate resulted that TV viewing is an important determinant of changes of concept of social realities (Lau, 2015, p.13). A study examined the behavior of twelve four-year-olds who viewed a Woody Woodpecker cartoon comprising many violent episodes with that of twelve other four-year-olds who viewed "The Little Red Hen," a nonviolent cartoon. The Woody viewers were much more violent than the The Little Red Hen (Heller & Heller, 2018). Cultivation theory was introduced by George Gerbner, the dean of Annenberg School of Communications at the University of Pennsylvania in 1960's. Cultivation theory examined the "long-term effects of television on heavy viewers" (Gerbner& Gross, 1976b, p.172). Cultivation

theory was further assumed into main streaming, mean world syndrome, resonance or double dose effect (Gerbner, 1980a, p.10).

The mean world syndrome effect on the audience where viewer's individual involvements in crime and violence, heavy viewing of TV programs become more fearful and think that the TV content is real and also world is not a place to live, resulted in a mean world syndrome effect (Gerbner, Gross, & Morgan, 1980b, p.21). After going through work presented by theorists whether there is relation in exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films and mean world syndrome effect in youth.

Research Design

A quantitative research method adopted to survey using questionnaire as a tool to collect the data in a face-to-face meetings from 300 respondents. For survey, the list of universities from HEC was obtained and three universities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad i.e. Bahria University, Islamabad, Foundation University Rawalpindi Campus and International Islamic University Islamabad were selected. Random sampling method was used.

Procedure

The questionnaires were furnished among youth, filled in person by the respondents and face to face discussions were also carried out. The researcher has adopted simple purposive sampling for survey. The list of universities was obtained by HEC after which three universities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad i.e. Bahria University, IIUI, and Foundation University Rawalpindi Campus were selected.

Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data from survey SPSS 21 was used. Cronbach's alpha reliability, mean and standard deviation were obtained before the inferential statistics. Pearson Correlation applied for finding the relationship among the variables and factorial analysis test was applied to test the hypothesis.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.708	20

The above table shows that the alpha reliability value is .708, which shows that data is acceptable.

Testing Hypothesis 1

Gender	
Male	50 (50%)
Female	49(49%)
Age of Respondents	
Teenagers:	16-19Years

Number of Hours Spending on Watching TV

2hrs	49(49%)
4hrs	51(51%)

Factor Analysis

Mean World Syndrome Effect and amount of fearfulness and real world perception factor analysis was carried out.

Table 2

Factor Analysis of Mean World Syndrome Effect and amount of fearfulness and real world perception

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	h^2
Amount of Fearfulness					
Fear Increased	2.67	.996	.617		.453
Stress Increased	2.71	1.102	.676		.432
Fear of Involvement in violent activities	2.62	1.211	.611		.411
Real World Perception					

Film is Real	2.46	1.513	.613	.504
World is Dangerous Place	2.18	1.011	.615	.517
Mistrust of people	2.34	1.131	.652	.531
% of Variance			13.791	9.361
				41.371

In table 2, Factor Analysis of Mean World Syndrome Effect and amount of fearfulness due to frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films and real world perception and frequent exposure of disaster apocalyptic films measured the mean, standard deviation, h2 and Variance of all the variables used in the research article.

To test the main hypothesis H1: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the mean world syndrome effect cultivated in youth. The following analysis was carried out on sub hypotheses.

As H1a: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the fearfulness in youth, analyzed as follow.

Table 3

Exposure of Disaster in Apocalyptic films	Amount of Fearfulness			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed) P-(Value)
Watching for 2 hours	2.08	4.81	.411*	.031
Watching for 4 hours or more	2.43	.601	.151*	.041

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 indicates that amount of fearfulness and frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films for 2 hours is correlated ($r = .411^*$, $P=.031$) that is significance. Table also indicates that amount of fearfulness and frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films for 4 hours is also correlated ($r = .151^*$, $P=.041$) that is significance. H1a is supported.

As H1b: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the real world perception in youth, analyzed below.

Table 4 indicates that real world perception and exposure of disaster in apocalyptic films for 2 hours is not correlated ($r = .581^*$, $P=.021$) that is significance. It also showed that real world perception and exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films for 4 and more hours is correlated ($r = .161^*$, $P=.043$) that is also highly significance.

Table 4

Exposure of Disaster in Apocalyptic films (in hours)	Real World Perception			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed) P-Value
Watching for 2 hrs	2.08	4.41	.581*	.021
Watching for 4 hrs or More	2.51	.601	.161*	.043

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

The research titled; Examining Mean World Syndrome Effect Cultivated in Youth by Exposure of Disaster of Apocalyptic Films, analyzed the relation between amount of fearfulness and frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films. It also examined the relation between exposure of disaster and real world perception among youth. Exposure of disaster comprised of two hours' exposure and four hours' exposure or more. Two hour exposure means that youth have watched the film for only one time whereas exposure for four hours or more means that respondents have watched the same film in one sitting for two times or more. Mean world syndrome

consists of fearfulness and real world perception. In today's world films are watched on television through Netflix and other services. Gerbner worked solely on violent program shown on television but not the films. Gerbner and Morgan supported the hypothesis of more exposure to violent or fearful content more likely to cultivate fear in children. Whereas, further studies revealed that it is not the exposure time, it's the content of the film that make children and youth fearful and change the fiction into reality. This study, though supporting the hypothesis of cultivation theory i.e., the more frequent exposure of disaster in apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the mean world effect cultivated in youth but on the other hand it is also supporting the fact that it is not time duration that is 2 or more matters or cumulative effect matters. It is the content of the film that has been exaggerated in a way that regardless of time of one, two three or four hours, there is effect on mind.

H1a: The more frequent exposure of disaster in apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the fearfulness in youth.

RQ1a: To what extent, exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films cultivate fearfulness in youth.

Finding revealed that 2 hours exposure and amount of fearfulness is correlated as $r = .411^*$ ($P=.031$) that is significance. The amount of fearfulness and frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films for 4 hours is correlated i.e., $r = .151^*$ ($P=.041$) that is significance. The more the respondents were exposed to apocalyptic films more

H1b: The more frequent exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, the more likely to be the real world perception in youth.

RQ1b: To what extent, exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films, cultivates real world perception in youth.

Table 4 indicates that real world perception and exposure of disaster in apocalyptic films for 2 hours is correlated ($r = .581^*$, $P=.021$) that is significance. It also showed that real world perception and exposure of disaster of apocalyptic films for 4 and more hours is correlated ($r = .161^*$, $P=.043$) that is also highly significance.

Conclusion

Mean world syndrome is not prolonged time dependent. More exposure have not cumulative effect on the viewers. This study analyzed that the effect on viewers whether watching for 2 hours or 4 hours. Viewers are exposed to the fearful content for 2 hours or more they perceive the world as a dangerous place and develop fear against the world whether they watch film containing disaster for one time or two times. The effect is same on all types of viewers.

References

- Bryant, J.; Mirion, D. (2004). "Theory and research in mass communication". *Journal of Communication*. 54 (4): 662–704. doi:10.1093/joc/54.4.662.
- Daud, K.A.M., Khidzir, N.Z., Ismail, A.R. and Abdullah, F.A. (2018), "Validity and reliability of instrument to measure social media skills among small and medium entrepreneurs at PengkalanDatu River", *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 1026-1037.
- Gerbner, G., Gross, L., Morgan, M., Signorielli, N., & Jackson-Beeck, M. (1979). The Demonstration of Power: Violence Profile. *Journal of Communication*, 29(10), 177-196.
- Gerbner, G.; Gross, L.; Morgan, M.; Signorielli, N. (1980a). "The "Mainstreaming" of America: Violence Profile No. 11". *Journal of Communication*. 30 (3): 10–29. doi:10.1111/j.1460-2466.1980.tb01987.x.
- Gerbner, G.; Gross, L.; Morgan, M.; Signorielli, N. (1980b). "The "Mainstreaming" of America: Violence Profile No. 11". *Journal of Communication*. 30 (3): 10–29. doi:10.1111/j.1460-2466.1980.tb01987.x.
- Gerbner, G. & Gross, L.(1976a). Living with television: The violence profile. *Journal of Communication*, 26(2), 172-199.doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1976.tb01397.
- Gerbner, G. & Gross, L.(1976b). Living with television: The violence profile. *Journal of Communication*, 26(2), 172-199.doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1976.tb01397.
- Griffin, E. (2012a). *Communication CommunicationCommunication*. New York: McGraw-Hill. pp. (8), 366–377
- Griffin, E. (2012b). *Communication CommunicationCommunication*. New York: McGraw-Hill. pp. (8), 366–377
- Gerbner, G., & Gross, L. (1976).Living with television: The violence profile. *Journal of communication*.
- Gerbner, G., Gross, L., Morgan, M., &Signorielli, N. (1980). The 'mainstreaming' of America: Violence profile no. 11. *Journal of Communication*, 30(Summer), 10–29.
- Griffin, E. (2012). *A First Look At Communication Theory*.New York: McGraw-HillCompanies, Inc.
- Heller, K., & Heller, K. (2018). *Cultivation Theory | Media Psychology*.

- Hughes, Michael (1980). "The Fruits of Cultivation Analysis: A Reexamination of Some Effects of Television Watching". *Public Opinion Quarterly*. 44 (3): 287–302. doi:10.1086/268597.
- Lau, Hey. (2015). Cultivation Effects of Television Broadcasting and Online Media. *New Media, Knowledge Practices and Multiliteracies* (pp.13-21).DOI: 10.1007/978-981-287-209-8_2
- Lee, Chul-joo&Niederdeppe, Jeff. (2011). Genre-Specific Cultivation Effects: Lagged Associations Between Overall TV Viewing, Local TV News Viewing, and Fatalistic Beliefs About Cancer Prevention. *Communication Research COMMUN RES.* 38 (6). 731-753. 10.1177/0093650210384990.
- Lippmann, W. (1921). *Public opinion*. New York: The MacMillan Company
- Yeung Lau, Hey.(2015). Cultivation Effects of Television Broadcasting and Online Media. 13-21. 10.1007/978-981-287-209-8_2.

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